

What are the main causes of rejection sensitive dysphoria in children with ADHD and how can we prevent RSD symptoms in the future?

Introduction

Attention deficit hyperactivity disorder (ADHD) is one of the most common neurodevelopmental disorders. According to the Center for ADHD Awareness Canada, “4-6% of adults and 5-7% of children, or approximately 1.8 million Canadians [have ADHD]. In other words, 1 of every 21 people in the country has the disorder.” Many people with attention deficit hyperactivity disorder have been relentlessly shamed by family, teachers, and peers for being overly sensitive. However, psychologists are now saying there is a link between those with ADHD and their heightened sensitivity when it comes to perceived rejection from others. This is called rejection sensitive dysphoria (RSD). In Greek, dysphoria means ‘unbearable’, emphasizing the extent of pain someone with RSD can experience. No one likes the feeling of rejection, but for those with RSD, the feelings are much more intense. An article from the board review and accredited Verywell Mind states, “These people expect to be rejected all the time. And as they anxiously look for signs that someone doesn’t want to be with them, they often behave in ways that push other people away. This behavior creates a painful cycle that can be difficult to break.” (Amy Morin, 2023). So, for all the people with ADHD who felt they were overdramatic or had something wrong with them because they had “big feelings,” it's not by choice; it's how ADHD brains are wired.

Stigma also exemplifies these feelings, as ADHD brains are still shown as being “abnormal” or “unhealthy”, which can be seen when googling scientific scans of ADHD brains and neurotypical brains. So, even with what should be reassuring information that those with ADHD just have different brains, some researchers label the brain without ADHD as normal, insinuating that the one with ADHD is abnormal, increasing stigma around the differences in neurodivergent and neurotypical brains. More concerning, these images were published less

than ten years ago by doctors. (See Appendix A). Unfortunately, there are limited studies and research done on rejection sensitivity dysphoria, and most of the findings and information are repetitive and lack discussion of how events in childhood can affect the chances of RSD later in life. The purpose of this research is to bring more awareness to rejection sensitive dysphoria and connect specific childhood events with later symptoms of rejection sensitive dysphoria.

This research is important as RSD is not discussed enough publicly and many people with ADHD don't know that they could be intensely affected by it. All existing studies state RSD is linked to ADHD through emotional dysregulation, leading to heightened pain from perceived rejection. Previous research has focused primarily on who RSD affects but not how it connects to childhood experiences, and therefore how it can be prevented. This study builds upon existing research while connecting specific childhood events to possible RSD symptoms in hopes to reduce future symptoms. By recognizing common events that children with ADHD experience that lead to high levels of RSD, it will be clear what precautions can be taken in the future to help eliminate RSD in the coming generations.

Literature review

In the 1990s, Dr. William Dodson coined the term Rejection Sensitive Dysphoria. “This label gained informal recognition within online ADHD communities” (Neff, 2023). Symptoms of RSD include things such as avoidance behaviors, negative self-talk, low self-esteem, hypervigilance, defensive reactions, social isolation, and more. “Dr. Dodson’s extensive research and clinical experience have led him to estimate that an overwhelming 99% of individuals with ADHD encounter Rejection Sensitive Dysphoria (RSD) at some point in their lives.” (Neff, 2023). These statistics underscore the impact RSD has on those with ADHD and show the importance of recognizing it as a huge aspect of ADHD management. An article by The ADHD

Center states, “Emotional hypersensitivity is a type of emotional dysregulation that causes low frustration tolerance, impulsivity, shortness of temper, emotional outbursts, and sudden mood changes” (2024), this is because ADHD brains process emotions differently than a brain without ADHD. Working memory is the cognitive system in charge of holding short-term information while using said information to conduct a task. This impacts problem-solving, learning, and the ability to reason. “Sometimes the working memory impairments of ADHD allow a momentary emotion to become too strong, flooding the brain with one intense emotion.” (Brown, 2025). This one emotion can become all-consuming and is too intense to simply stop thinking about. RSD can be triggered by real or perceived rejection, teasing, or criticism.

There is no specific cause for rejection-sensitive dysphoria, but psychologists and doctors have found common denominators. “RSD is a trauma-related response to involuntary unmasking. What appears as emotional overreaction often reflects the nervous system’s response to unmasking and thus perceived exposure, regardless of whether the person consciously recognizes it.” (Barnes, 2025). Masking, also known as camouflaging, refers to deliberately hiding symptoms of a disorder, in this case, ADHD, to conform to social norms and avoid stigma around symptoms. Masking can delay possible diagnoses of ADHD as symptoms are not being noticed. Being unaware of what is being masked can cause anxiety or depression, and a higher risk of developing a substance abuse disorder to cope with feelings. Other contributors to RSD include overreactive opioid receptors, dopamine deficiency, and even an overreactive amygdala. Natural opioid receptors aid in the control of pain receptors and help emotional hurt feel less intense. But in RSD, the opioid receptors can overreact, resulting in any perceived rejection feeling extremely painful. The brains reward system uses feel good chemicals like dopamine, which people gain when they are praised or experience some type of success. Many people with

ADHD experience dopamine deficiency, so things that should give them feel-good chemicals may not give them any or give them less than neurotypicals. An article from La Concierge Psychologist claims “some people’s brain chemistry may make them hypersensitive to losing that rewarding feeling of acceptance [dopamine]; hence, the emotional meltdown when faced with rejection.” (2024). The amygdala, the brain’s threat detector, can go into overdrive when it perceives rejection, making the feeling extremely difficult to manage.

When rejection sensitivity is externalized, it can appear as sudden bursts of rage, but it can also appear as suicidal thoughts. Unfortunately, in childhood, many people with ADHD are constantly told they are overdramatic or too sensitive due to feelings caused by RSD, so to avoid being judged for their feelings, they repress them, often leading to people pleasing tendencies. They also begin doing everything in their power to avoid criticism or rejection, and in some cases, they just completely stop trying in all aspects of life in hopes to avoid situations of distress, as “these adaptations, or personality tendencies, can cause other problems later on in life with relationships and can frustrate getting our needs heard and met in a healthy way.” (2024). These tendencies could impact someone's ability to stand up for themselves in any scenario, whether it be at the doctor's, in a toxic work environment, or in an abusive relationship. This can unfortunately decrease the chance of people with ADHD getting themselves the help they need and out of these dangerous situations.

There are many recommended coping strategies and treatments to reduce the symptoms of RSD. An article by the Cleveland Clinic explains, “because RSD isn’t an officially recognized medical condition, there aren’t any medications specifically approved to treat it. Instead, healthcare providers use a practice known as off-label prescribing.” (2025). Off-label prescribing is described as the practice of a healthcare provider prescribing medication for conditions, they

are not specifically approved to treat. This is legal and considered medically acceptable when medications have evidence to prove they have a low risk of being harmful to the consumer and are effective for the appropriate off-label use. Medication types used to treat RSD include Alpha-2 receptor agonists, stimulant medications, and monoamine oxidase inhibitor medications.

Alpha-2 receptor agonists are medications that activate a chemical receptor in neurons in specific areas of the brain. Clonidine and guanfacine are two types of medication that affect these receptors and make the areas more active. This makes it easier for the brain to regulate internal communication, reducing the effect of rejection-sensitive dysphoria. Stimulant medications increase levels of neurotransmitters in the brain. Neurotransmitters are chemical messenger molecules that the brain uses to communicate and activate or deactivate different processes in the brain. Increasing certain neurotransmitters' activity in certain areas of the brain will also increase dopamine levels. So stimulant medications like amphetamine/dextroamphetamine and methylphenidate help activate brain areas responsible for regulating communication. Monoamine oxidase inhibitor (MAOI) is a class of medications that treat depression, but experts are also aware that some of these medications, such as tranylcypromine, can also help with RSD. MAOIs impact what the consumer can eat, as certain foods, when they interact with MAOIs, can cause a dangerous spike in blood pressure. Unfortunately, MAOIs cannot be taken at the same time as common ADHD meds. This reduces the number of people who would be able to go down this treatment route, as ADHD and RSD are connected, but those who do not take ADHD medication could take MAOIs if their doctor feels comfortable prescribing it.

Non-medicated treatments are also available, such as psychotherapy, which can help those with rejection-sensitive dysphoria learn to process and manage feelings, so they feel less overwhelmed. Therapy can also develop skills to reframe negative thoughts, develop coping

strategies, build self-esteem, and enhance emotional regulation. Amy Morin, licensed psychotherapist, recommends to “start by talking to your physician, who can assist you with determining the appropriate next steps. Many times, cognitive behavioral therapy can help you deal with the thoughts, feelings, and behaviors that fuel the fear of rejection.” (Morin, 2023). However, this approach does not work for everyone, making prevention the more realistic option.

To summarize, all existing studies state that RSD is linked to ADHD through emotional dysregulation, leading to the heightened pain from perceived rejection. These all leave negative impacts on the lives of those with ADHD. And currently RSD research is being conducted to help those with RSD but not to prevent the problem in the first place. Current treatments for RSD include off-label prescriptions and psychotherapies. However, these do not work for everyone and as a society we should aim to increase the well-being of children. This can be done through more causation research being done on children with ADHD and later symptoms of RSD.

Methodology

This study was conducted using a mixed method approach, including qualitative and quantitative sections. Interviews were conducted with two educators, a high school teacher and a kindergarten teacher. They were chosen based on their teaching qualifications through local school websites. This was done to gain perspective on how these educators have observed children with ADHD interact with their peers and respond to directions, as well as parent reactions and responses revolving around their child having ADHD. These interviews were done voluntarily and the interviewee stayed unnamed in the research. However, the interviews were recorded to ensure quotes were stated correctly, and all information could be recalled and looked back on. Online surveys were also conducted using a seven-point statement-based Likert scale.

They were distributed by displaying posters around 3 high schools in the Fraser Valley with a quick response code (QR code), as well as being posted on local social media groups based on neurodiversity. Multiple licensed therapists and counselors were also given the QR code. This survey was advertised only for high schoolers diagnosed with ADHD and to ensure full transparency respondents were asked if they are clinically diagnosed, self-diagnosed, or not diagnosed at all. This way, those who selected self-diagnosed or were not diagnosed were removed from the results. Those with conflicting responses were also removed such as not having a diagnosis but taking medication specifically for ADHD as it cannot be assumed that they meant to select if they were diagnosed or got a stimulant used for ADHD for another reason.

A control group survey was also conducted and filled out by twenty recipients to keep the sample size the same. They were distributed through QR codes around schools as well, and participants were instructed to only fill it out if they did not have diagnosed ADHD. Data from these surveys were then analyzed to find statistical significance through a one-way ANOVA between the two groups, and data was further analyzed for those found to be significant. The control group and experimental group both answered questions through the Likert scale based on how they relate to different statements (See appendix B-AC). The Likert scale results were transferred into their corresponding number to allow easier analyzation of results. For example, “strongly disagree” would be calculated as a 1, while “strongly agree” would be a 7. All recipient responses were numbered 1 through 20. In the experimental group numbers were labeled with the letter A and those in the control group were labeled with a B. The numerical data was then organized in tables with a column for the experimental group (A) and the control group (B) to compare similarities and differences. It should also be acknowledged that surveys were filled out by convenient groups of people (see limitations). To ensure the ethics of the research due to its

confidential and personal nature, the surveys which were formatted using Google Forms were selected in the settings to not connect emails to the survey responses to keep them anonymous. Participants all filled out the surveys voluntarily and could stop at any point if they didn't feel comfortable; they were instructed to stop and not submit the form. For full transparency, all survey participants had to select a box stating they consent to their answers being used in research.

Data analysis

Data from surveys was analyzed by calculating the mean, median, and mode of all the questions within their respective group (control or experimental). The data was then calculated to find statistical significance using one way ANOVA test. Datacamp explains “A one-way ANOVA test is used when there is one independent variable with two or more groups. The objective is to determine whether a significant difference exists between the means of different groups” (2024). Many of the statements participants were asked to evaluate held no statistical significance. Such as “I felt misunderstood as a child” ($F(1, 38) = 3.26, p = .079, \eta^2 = 0.08$). “On school report cards I was told I don’t engage in class discussions enough” ($F(1, 38) = 2.14, p = .152, \eta^2 = 0.05$). “I perceive people’s neutral reactions in tone or body language as rejection” ($F(1, 38) = 1.47, p = .233, \eta^2 = 0.04$). “I try to achieve perfection to avoid chances of failing or disapproval” ($F(1, 38) = 0.55, p = .465, \eta^2 = 0.01$). “I avoid social interactions and trying new things due to fear of social rejection or disapproval” ($F(1, 38) = 0.38, p = .540, \eta^2 = 0.01$). “I avoid intimacy out of fear others will not like the real me” ($F(1, 38) = 0.70, p = .407, \eta^2 = 0.02$). “I find relationships draining” ($F(1, 38) = 3.06, p = .088, \eta^2 = 0.07$). “I have low self-esteem which presents as extreme self-doubt or negative self-talk” ($F(1, 38) = 4.06, p = .051, \eta^2 = 0.10$). “I display people pleasing tendencies” ($F(1, 38) = 3.42, p = .072, \eta^2 = 0.08$). Even though these

responses did not have a significant difference in means between the control group and experimental group, the results are still important as they are part of the research but show there is not a big change in responses from those with ADHD and those without.

The analysis will focus on the following statements.

“When someone with authority asks to talk to me my initial reaction is fear” ($F(1, 38) = 7.50, p = .009, \eta^2 = 0.16$). It was calculated to be a 16.5% variance between the different groups. “When a friend or loved one asks to talk to me my initial reaction is fear” ($F(1, 38) = 8.18, p = .007, \eta^2 = 0.18$). Similar to the previous statement there was found to be a 17.7% variance. “In my childhood I was constantly told I was weird” ($F(1, 38) = 33.06, p < .001, \eta^2 = 0.47$). The biggest statistical difference was calculated here with a variance of 46.5%. “In my childhood I did not have many close friends” ($F(1, 38) = 8.86, p = .005, \eta^2 = 0.19$). An 18.9% variance was found. “When I feel sadness or anger, I am overcome by extreme emotions” ($F(1, 38) = 10.62, p = .002, \eta^2 = 0.22$). 21.8% variance appeared. “I have difficulty managing and controlling my emotions leading me to feel shame” ($F(1, 38) = 18.65, p < .001, \eta^2 = 0.33$). For this statement the variance was 32.9%.

The questions below asked survey participants how they resonate with different instances when they were in elementary school.

“I was constantly told to try harder” ($F(1, 38) = 4.17, p = .048, \eta^2 = 0.10$). A lower variance was calculated as the variance fell to 9.9%. “I was constantly told to pay attention” ($F(1, 38) = 11.65, p = .002, \eta^2 = 0.23$). A drastic difference was found here as the variance was 23.5%. “I was constantly told to sit still” ($F(1, 38) = 18.87, p < .001, \eta^2 = 0.33$). A variance of 33.2% is shown. “I was labeled as inconsistent in work” ($F(1, 38) = 7.92, p = .008, \eta^2 = 0.17$). A 17.3%

variance was found. “I was said to struggle staying on task” ($F(1, 38) = 23.08, p < .001, \eta^2 = 0.38$). A big statistic difference was calculated at 37.8% variance as the mean for the control group was half of the experimental group. “I was said to be disruptive in class” ($F(1, 38) = 11.54, p = .002, \eta^2 = 0.23$). Variance was calculated at 23.3%. “I received more criticism than my peers” ($F(1, 38) = 6.04, p = .019, \eta^2 = 0.14$). There was found to be a 13.7% variance. For all statements above the variance was due to the experimental group consistently relating more strongly to said statements. (See Appendix B-AC for data tables).

ADHD participants were asked if they took ADHD medication. 50.0% claimed they did, 45.0% said they did not and 5.0% did not feel comfortable answering. ADHD participants were also asked if their parents allowed them the opportunity to receive medication for ADHD in their childhood. 80.0% of participants agreed to some extent that they had the ability to get medication while 15.0% disagreed and 5.0% were neutral. By comparing these results with the participants who currently take medication on a chart, those who agreed to some extent that they had access to medication were not more likely to take it later but those who were not allowed medication were less likely to take it.

Interviews

A common theme brought up when interviewing a high school teacher and a kindergarten teacher was stigma surrounding ADHD. As previously stated within the literature review, stigma and the behavior associated with it can increase RSD symptoms. When asked how parents have responded to comments on children's behavior and the possibility of getting assessed by a pediatrician for ADHD, the kindergarten teacher (teacher A) explained she will approach parents and start conversations with the following.

“[I say to parents] here are the things that I've noticed, and these stand out from what would be typical of a 4 or 5-year-old, 6-year-old in class. And this is why it would be worthwhile to get looked at. And quite often, parents will say well, first we're going to. And then they have a list of things that they think might help. Like we're going to change their diet. We're going to go to the chiropractor. We're going to try to get them better sleep schedule and this and that, and I'm not saying that those things are bad. But if your child's brain is wired in a certain way, those are not going to change your child's brain's wiring. So, that always makes me frustrated for the child, especially when I see children in my classroom, who literally are crawling out of their skin, because they can't focus. They're falling out of chairs. They're, like, they're completely inattentive. They're struggling so much, regardless of how many fidgets I give them, wiggle cushions, and opportunities to stand instead of sitting. And work. It doesn't matter. We've thrown everything we can think of at this child to try to help them, and it's not working. And then we're begging parents and parents to be like, well, we'll see. But my biggest frustration is the pediatricians who say, well let's just see what happens when they're older. That is my biggest frustration.”

For teachers of all grades, there are only so many tools available to them to support students. Especially when said students are not receiving appropriate support from parents and pediatricians. In kindergarten many children are being looked at by an education professional for the first time in an observative way to flag student behaviors. Unfortunately, when these concerns regarding behavior and in class struggles are brought up to parents, some are not eager to seek further help for their child. And as stated above by teacher A, parents have tried to “fix” their child by changing things like sleep schedules and diet. This can benefit the child as sleep and nutrition are important and can help alertness and behavior, but it cannot “fix” or change

how a brain functions. And in trying other ways to “fix” a child, it insinuates once again that there is something wrong. By accepting the possibility of a child having ADHD and seeking the proper professionals for diagnosis, it not only helps a child succeed in school but shows them that it is something that should be talked about openly and not shamed. Similarly, teacher B stated, “I’ve definitely had, parents who do not wish to have their child diagnosed, even if they’re struggling, and the fear is usually out of the label and potential perceived limitations it might cost.” Both accounts of parent’s responses show a lack of true knowledge people have on what ADHD is. Teacher A expands on this saying ADHD children are “going to be labelled regardless [of a diagnosis], so they’re going to be labelled as the naughty kid, the kid who’s out of control, the kid who doesn’t pay attention, or potentially a child with ADHD who needs some support.” When educators and other adults are aware of how a child’s brain works, they can best understand why this child is doing what they are doing and therefore better support them without making them feel like a “bad kid”.

Most importantly, teacher A explained frustration with pediatricians. She acknowledged the fact that it can be more difficult for someone to tell whether behavior is typical or not. However, most kindergarteners she has referred to pediatricians will not have an in-person appointment with the parent and child but instead have it over the phone with only one parent/guardian. And usually, her students have been told by these pediatricians that “we will see what happens when they get older”. The doctors only information on this child would then be the parent’s word which they do not see how their child acts in a classroom and a form filled out by the child’s teacher. Without even laying eyes on said child they are saying to wait till they are older to get properly assessed, which effectively sabotages said child’s understanding of themselves and prevents them from receiving the help they need and deserve. Without a diagnosis, it is much

more likely a child will grow up with shame wondering why they are the way they are. But with a diagnosis they can learn to have grace for themselves as they are not “broken” or “bad”. Sadly 60% of survey participants from the experimental group agreed to some degree that their parents spoke or acted negatively to their ADHD symptoms in their childhood increasing their later RSD symptoms.

Parenting books

To gain perspective on how parents of children with ADHD are being guided or helped, many parenting books about raising children with ADHD were analyzed. How parents are guided throughout their journey of parenting with an ADHD child can greatly impact their view on how their child's brain works and how to best communicate and connect with them. Through a local public library, many books available about ADHD and parenting were read and annotated. Books such as Doctor Sharon Salines’ “What Your ADHD Child Wishes You Knew” portray a positive view on children with ADHD. It encourages parents to educate themselves on their child's brain and accommodate their parenting accordingly. She introduces a parenting method called the 5 Cs which include self-control, compassion, collaboration, consistency, and celebration (pages 7-9). She wants parents to meet their child where they are to build the child's self-esteem and teach them the tools they need to be successful in the future. Doctor Saline stresses the importance of self-control as the first C because if a parent is struggling to manage their feelings they will not be able to effectively communicate rationally with their child and show their child the skills they need to manage their own emotions. Compassion will help parents meet their child where they are at in the moment instead of where such parent expects their child to be. Collaboration is vital when parenting in general as children should feel heard and seen. For those with ADHD they can feel dismissed as they are not living in a world made

for their brains. When parents take a collaborative approach their ADHD child will feel included and not dismissed when creating plans for things such as before school routines or ways to make transitions easier. If a child feels they have a say in matters affecting their everyday life they can go into implementing these with an attitude of teamwork instead of feeling dismissed or punished as these things are happening to them and not with them. Consistency within parenting is important when boundaries are set, especially with a child who has ADHD based on these books. Kids naturally try to test boundaries and see what they can get away with. If parents are inconsistent with what they tolerate it can cause confusion because sometimes they get in trouble for doing something and other times they do not, which can lead to overthinking and shame. The last C is celebration. Especially when looking at parenting through the lens of RSD in children with ADHD it's clear they should be celebrated not just for what may be seen as a huge accomplishment but also doing things that can be difficult for them such as showering or doing their homework. Since neurodivergent children receive high amounts of criticism, their self-worth and confidence often are weak, so they need more reassurance than others. Implementing these 5 C's in parenting can help children with ADHD grow in an environment that is understanding and accommodating to their brain. When proper measures are taken such as the 5 C's, ADHD children will not only have a better sense of what works for them, but they will see skills like self-control displayed in their parents and be more willing to learn.

Unfortunately, for every two factual books around parenting children with ADHD there is one that increases stigma and is targeted at parents. This is incredibly concerning to progress as a parent who is picking up a book about how to best help their child wants to learn and grow as a parent and learn what is happening in their child's mind. However, if they have no prior knowledge of ADHD when they pick up a book written by a doctor or someone with a PhD, they

are likely to believe what they are being told even when it is incorrect information that has been formerly disproved and can harm their child long-term.

Limitations

It is crucial to identify limitations when analyzing data to highlight possible factors that could sway data results. The main limitation present was the mode of distribution of surveys. Quick response (QR) codes for participants with ADHD were given to multiple high schools, therapists, and were posted on neurodiversity-based Facebook pages. Due to counselors displaying the QR codes and making their high school clients with ADHD aware, it would therefore affect the number of participants that check “yes” when asked if they currently receive counseling/therapy from a licensed professional. Therefore, it cannot be said that 50% of high schoolers with ADHD receive counseling support because those that did were more likely to be exposed to the option of taking the survey. Originally, surveys were going to be distributed through high schools' diverse ability coordinator but due to confidentiality concerns it was not realistic. Through diverse ability coordinators it would be known if someone has a proper ADHD diagnosis, and by allowing anyone to take the survey and hope they are truthful when they claim they are diagnosed with ADHD it can't be confirmed. Additionally, due to surveys being put on three Facebook groups, people who are not in high school could decide to fill it out despite the clear focus group. Another important limitation is the survey participation size and demographic. A lack of male participation causes an imbalance when analyzing the survey responses. It was hoped participants would be 50% male identifying and 50% female. However, within the ADHD participant survey 70% was female and 30% was male and was the same for the control group survey. Therefore, due to the small amount of survey participants and unequal data collected on each gender, this study cannot be used to view RSD as a whole. However, it does give a good

insight into the similarities of those with attention deficit hyperactivity disorder and how it affected these individuals later.

Discussion

Through this study, it was found that those with ADHD reported higher levels of sensitivity along with childhood events that can increase a child's chance of getting RSD symptoms than the control group no matter the amount of criticism faced in childhood. Through interviews with educators as well as more thorough research from external resources such as Doctors like Sharon Salines book "What Your ADHD Child Wishes You Knew" parenting and overall communication tactics have been shown to reduce the significance of RSD symptoms. However, it should be acknowledged that Dr. Saline's parenting strategies, such as the 5 C's were not specifically designed to help RSD. To ensure children with ADHD can receive care best fit for them, parents of neurodivergent children along with all educators and support workers should be encouraged to read books like Saline's and seek out external education on how to best support and communicate with children who have brains that are wired differently. Books going into public libraries should also be better assessed to ensure false information and parenting tactics are not being spread to vulnerable parents.

Most importantly, children with ADHD should not receive "special treatment". They should be provided with adults who are able to communicate with them in an effective way that will improve their wellbeing, and they should be taught tools to live their everyday life in ways compatible with their respective ADHD symptoms. However, it is hard for children to get a diagnosis while they are building the skills to co-exist in group settings like school. During an interview with a kindergarten teacher, she expressed frustration with the current diagnosing practices she has observed as was mentioned above.

Annotated Bibliography

About ADHD. CADDAC. (n.d.-b). [https://caddac.ca/about-adhd/#:~:text=Attention%20Deficit%20Hyperactivity%20Disorder%20\(ADHD,the%20country%20has%20the%20disorder.](https://caddac.ca/about-adhd/#:~:text=Attention%20Deficit%20Hyperactivity%20Disorder%20(ADHD,the%20country%20has%20the%20disorder.)

ANOVA test: An in-depth guide with examples | datacamp. Datacamp. (2024, September 20). <https://www.datacamp.com/tutorial/anova-test>

Morin, A. (2025, September 23). *Understanding rejection sensitivity and how it can affect you.* Verywell Mind. <https://www.verywellmind.com/what-is-rejection-sensitivity-4682652>

Barnes, Rachel, M. A. (2025, June 17). *“is rejection sensitivity a trauma response?”* ADDitude. <https://www.additudemag.com/rejection-sensitivity-adhd-trauma-unmasking/>

Berenson, K. R., Gyurak, A., Ayduk, O., Downey, G., Garner, M. J., Mogg, K., Bradley, B. P., & Pine, D. S. (2009, December 1). *Rejection sensitivity and disruption of attention by social threat cues.* *Journal of research in personality.* <https://pmc.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/articles/PMC2771869/>

Bertin, M., Johns, B. H., & Kuhl, K. (2025, September 5). *7 surprising ways ADHD shows up in the classroom.* ADDitude. https://www.additudemag.com/adhd-in-the-classroom-schoolbehavior/?srsltid=AfmBOoqWUOeFvXMBIZjKflsY20sc7paS9fwZ4hzPqZBVJ3_Re4gT5qmo

Brown, T. E. (2025, March 19). *Exaggerated emotions: How and why ADHD triggers intense feelings.* ADDitude. <https://www.additudemag.com/slideshows/adhd-emotions-understanding-intense-feelings/>

Cuncic, A. (2024, May 10). *What is ADHD masking?.* Verywell Mind. <https://www.verywellmind.com/what-is-adhd-masking-5200863>

Evolution and ADHD. Columbia University Department of Psychiatry. (2024, March 4). [https://www.columbiapsychiatry.org/research/research-areas/child-and-adolescent-psychiatry/sultan-lab-mental-health-informatics/research-areas/evolutionary-psychiatry/evolution-and-adhd\](https://www.columbiapsychiatry.org/research/research-areas/child-and-adolescent-psychiatry/sultan-lab-mental-health-informatics/research-areas/evolutionary-psychiatry/evolution-and-adhd/)

How to manage rejection sensitive dysphoria (RSD) for adults with ADHD. LA Concierge Psychologist. (2024, October 10).

<https://laconciergepsychologist.com/blog/rejection-sensitive-dysphoria-adhd/>

Jittayuthd, S., & Karl, A. (2022, January 28). *Rejection sensitivity and vulnerable attachment: Associations with social support and PTSD symptoms in trauma survivors.* European journal of psychotraumatology.

<https://pmc.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/articles/PMC8803066/>

Kirsten, A. (2025b, June 2). *Rejection sensitive dysphoria and ADHD: What parents need to know - today's parent.* Today's Parent.

<https://www.todaysparent.com/kids/rejection-sensitive-dysphoria-and-adhd-what-parents-need-to-know/>

Mikami, A. Y., et al, (2015). Implications of parental affiliate stigma in families of children with ADHD. *Journal of clinical child and adolescent psychology : the official journal for the Society of Clinical Child and Adolescent Psychology, American Psychological Association, Division 53*, <https://pmc.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/articles/PMC4383715/>

Neff, Dr. M. A. (2023, November 8). *Rejection sensitivity dysphoria (RSD) and ADHD: Root causes & support.* Neurodivergent Insights.

https://neurodivergentinsights.com/history-of-rejection-sensitive-dysphoria/?srsltid=AfmBOork2ofpSq8mUW67NKuA487awRjANVU_ipa9icDVBgLLcmQYedu

Olfson, Mark, et al. "Treatment of US Children with Attention-Deficit/Hyperactivity Disorder in the Adolescent Brain Cognitive Development Study." *JAMA Network Open*, U.S.

National Library of Medicine, 3 Apr. 2023,
pmc.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/articles/PMC10148191/.

Reclaim your voice, rewrite your story. Rejection Sensitivity Dysphoria and ADHD | Barrie Therapist | VOX Mental Health. (2024, July 4).

<https://www.voxmentalhealth.com/blogs/understanding-and-managing-rejection-sensitive-dysphoria-rsd>

Rejection sensitive dysphoria (RSD): Symptoms & treatment. Cleveland Clinic. (2025, June 2). <https://my.clevelandclinic.org/health/diseases/24099-rejection-sensitive-dysphoria-rsd>

Rejection sensitive dysphoria: 10 signs you might have RSD and 5 ways to manage it.
Newport Institute. (2024, February 14).
<https://www.newportinstitute.com/resources/mental-health/rejection-sensitive-dysphoria/>

Saline, S., Markham, L., & Campbell, C. (2018). *What your ADHD child wishes you knew: Working together to Empower Kids for success in school and life.* TarcherPerigee.

Staniland, J. (2019, December). *ADHD and complex trauma.* Child Development Clinic.
<https://www.childdevelopmentclinic.com.au/adhd-and-complex-trauma.html>

The ADHD Centre. (2024, September 9). *ADHD and hypersensitivity – physical and emotional issues.* The ADHD Centre. <https://www.adhdcentre.co.uk/adhd-and-hypersensitivity-physical-and-emotional-issues/>

Wachsman, M. W. (2025, June 17). *Emotional dysregulation is a core, taxing ADHD trait: New study.* ADDitude. <https://www.additudemag.com/emotional-stability-adhd-assessment-personality-traits/>

Wilkins, F., & Nikolaidis, A. (2025, September 3). *How is the ADHD brain different?.* Child Mind Institute. <https://childmind.org/article/how-is-the-adhd-brain-different/>

10 things you should never say to your child. ADDitude. (2022, April 14).
<https://www.additudemag.com/slideshows/what-not-to-say-to-an-adhd-child/?srsltid=AfmBOoqpHe9ADNF9ciPHFGd0V9WL4uA7qgvGWtlyMr-WEGvDQrqaA1kS>

Appendix A

ADHD

Image from NeuroGrow Brain Fitness Center comparing a brain with attention sensitive hyperactivity disorder with a “healthy brain”.

“Dr. Fotuhi: Best Neurologist: Author: Speaker.” *NeuroGrow Brain Fitness Center Neurology Clinic*, 11 Dec. 2019, neurogrow.com/add-vs-adhd-and-the-different-types-of-adhd/.

Image from ADD+ADHD Solutions comparing a child with ADHDs brain and a child without being labeled as a “normal brain”.

Nophsker, Christian. “Differences in Brain Structure for Children with A.D.H.D.” *ADD & ADHD Solutions*, Christian Nophsker, 10 Apr. 2018, www.addsolutionsnj.com/differences-in-brain-structure-for-children-with-a-d-h-d/.

Appendix B

"In elementary school I received more criticism than my peers."

	A-ADHD	B-Control
Respondent 1	2	5
Respondent 2	7	5
Respondent 3	5	6
Respondent 4	6	4
Respondent 5	5	2
Respondent 6	7	2
Respondent 7	6	2
Respondent 8	7	4
Respondent 9	7	4
Respondent 10	6	2
Respondent 11	2	7
Respondent 12	5	4
Respondent 13	5	4
Respondent 14	6	5
Respondent 15	6	2
Respondent 16	4	2
Respondent 17	6	5
Respondent 18	2	5
Respondent 19	4	2
Respondent 20	4	5

$F(1, 38) = 6.04, p = .019, \eta^2 = 0.14.$

A. Mean-5.1

Median-5.5

Mode-6

B. Mean-3.8

Median-4

Mode-2

Appendix C

"I display people pleasing tendencies."

	A-ADHD	B-Control
Respondent 1	3	2
Respondent 2	6	6
Respondent 3	6	7
Respondent 4	4	6
Respondent 5	6	5
Respondent 6	7	2
Respondent 7	6	6
Respondent 8	5	7
Respondent 9	6	6
Respondent 10	7	4
Respondent 11	6	6
Respondent 12	7	4
Respondent 13	5	4
Respondent 14	7	6
Respondent 15	7	5
Respondent 16	6	5
Respondent 17	7	6
Respondent 18	5	7
Respondent 19	7	3
Respondent 20	7	7

$F(1, 38) = 3.42, p = .072, \eta^2 = 0.08.$

A. Mean-6.35

Median-6

Mode-7

B. Mean-5.2

Median-6

Mode-6

Appendix D

"I have low self-esteem which presents as extreme self-doubt or negative self-talk."

	A-ADHD	B-Control
Respondent 1	2	2
Respondent 2	6	7
Respondent 3	6	5
Respondent 4	7	5
Respondent 5	6	6
Respondent 6	7	4
Respondent 7	6	5
Respondent 8	4	5
Respondent 9	5	5
Respondent 10	6	3
Respondent 11	5	5
Respondent 12	6	5
Respondent 13	7	5
Respondent 14	7	4
Respondent 15	6	2
Respondent 16	3	5
Respondent 17	4	6
Respondent 18	5	6
Respondent 19	7	4
Respondent 20	5	4

$F(1, 38) = 4.06, p = .051, \eta^2 = 0.10$

A. Mean-5.5

Median-6

Mode-6

B. Mean-4.65

Median-5

Mode-5

Appendix E

"When someone with authority asks to talk to me my initial reaction is fear."

	A-ADHD	B-Control
Respondent 1	5	5
Respondent 2	7	6
Respondent 3	7	2
Respondent 4	6	7
Respondent 5	5	6
Respondent 6	7	7
Respondent 7	6	6
Respondent 8	5	6
Respondent 9	5	4
Respondent 10	5	5
Respondent 11	6	5
Respondent 12	7	5
Respondent 13	5	5
Respondent 14	7	3
Respondent 15	7	5
Respondent 16	5	6
Respondent 17	7	6
Respondent 18	7	5
Respondent 19	7	4

$F(1, 38) = 7.50, p = .009, \eta^2 = 0.16.$

A. Median-6.5

Mode-7

B. Mean-5.2

Median-5

Mode-5,6

Appendix F

"When a friend or loved one asks to talk to me my initial reaction is fear."

	A-ADHD	B-Control
Respondent 1	2	2
Respondent 2	7	6
Respondent 3	7	1
Respondent 4	7	4
Respondent 5	1	2
Respondent 6	5	3
Respondent 7	7	2
Respondent 8	5	6
Respondent 9	2	2
Respondent 10	6	6
Respondent 11	4	5
Respondent 12	7	4
Respondent 13	5	4
Respondent 14	7	5
Respondent 15	7	3
Respondent 16	2	4
Respondent 17	7	5
Respondent 18	6	3
Respondent 19	7	3
Respondent 20	7	5

$F(1, 38) = 8.18, p = .007, \eta^2 = 0.18.$

A. Mean-5.4

Median-6.5

Mode-7

B. Mean-3.75

Median-4

Mode-2,4,3,5

Appendix G

"When I feel sadness or anger, I am overcome by extreme emotions."

	A-ADHD	B-Control
Respondent 1	3	6
Respondent 2	6	6
Respondent 3	6	2
Respondent 4	6	2
Respondent 5	4	2
Respondent 6	7	7
Respondent 7	7	4
Respondent 8	6	7
Respondent 9	6	2
Respondent 10	7	5
Respondent 11	6	6
Respondent 12	6	4
Respondent 13	7	4
Respondent 14	7	6
Respondent 15	7	2
Respondent 16	5	4
Respondent 17	5	6
Respondent 18	7	6
Respondent 19	7	3
Respondent 20	6	6

$F(1, 38) = 10.62, p = .002, \eta^2 = 0.22.$

A. Mean-6.05

Median-6

Mode-6,7

B. Mean-4.5

Median-4.5

Mode-6

Appendix H

"I have difficulty managing and controlling my emotions leading me to feel shame."

	A-ADHD	B-Control
Respondent 1	4	2
Respondent 2	7	5
Respondent 3	5	2
Respondent 4	7	2
Respondent 5	4	5
Respondent 6	7	6
Respondent 7	4	3
Respondent 8	5	5
Respondent 9	4	2
Respondent 10	6	5
Respondent 11	5	4
Respondent 12	5	4
Respondent 13	7	4
Respondent 14	7	2
Respondent 15	6	2
Respondent 16	5	2
Respondent 17	7	5
Respondent 18	6	5
Respondent 19	7	6
Respondent 20	5	5

$F(1, 38) = 18.65, p < .001, \eta^2 = 0.33.$

A. Mean-5.65

Median-5.5

Mode-7

B. Mean-3.8

Median-4

Mode-2,5

Appendix I

"I find relationships draining."

	A-ADHD	B-Control
Respondent 1	3	4
Respondent 2	5	5
Respondent 3	6	5
Respondent 4	5	7
Respondent 5	6	4
Respondent 6	5	6
Respondent 7	7	3
Respondent 8	4	5
Respondent 9	5	1
Respondent 10	4	6
Respondent 11	5	6
Respondent 12	6	4
Respondent 13	6	4
Respondent 14	6	4
Respondent 15	6	1
Respondent 16	4	6
Respondent 17	5	2
Respondent 18	6	5
Respondent 19	7	6
Respondent 20	6	7

$F(1, 38) = 3.06, p = .088, \eta^2 = 0.07.$

A. Mean-5.35

Median-5.5

Mode-6

B. Mean-4.55

Median-5

Mode-4,6

Appendix J

"I avoid intimacy out of fear others will not like the real me."

	A-ADHD	B-Control
Respondent 1	2	2
Respondent 2	5	6
Respondent 3	5	4
Respondent 4	5	6
Respondent 5	2	5
Respondent 6	6	5
Respondent 7	7	2
Respondent 8	3	6
Respondent 9	2	2
Respondent 10	3	2
Respondent 11	6	7
Respondent 12	7	2
Respondent 13	7	2
Respondent 14	3	5
Respondent 15	6	1
Respondent 16	4	7
Respondent 17	6	5
Respondent 18	6	5
Respondent 19	7	6
Respondent 20	4	6

$F(1, 38) = 0.70, p = .407, \eta^2 = 0.02.$

A. Mean-4.8

Median-5

Mode-6

B. Mean-4.3

Median-5

Mode-2

Appendix K

"I avoid social interactions and trying new things due to fear of social rejection or disapproval."

	A-ADHD	B-Control
Respondent 1	1	2
Respondent 2	7	7
Respondent 3	6	6
Respondent 4	3	7
Respondent 5	4	6
Respondent 6	7	5
Respondent 7	7	5
Respondent 8	4	5
Respondent 9	2	2
Respondent 10	3	5
Respondent 11	4	7
Respondent 12	6	4
Respondent 13	7	4
Respondent 14	6	5
Respondent 15	7	2
Respondent 16	3	4
Respondent 17	7	3
Respondent 18	6	5
Respondent 19	7	6
Respondent 20	6	6

$F(1, 38) = 0.38, p = .540, \eta^2 = 0.01.$

A. Mean-5.15

Median-6

Mode-7

B. Mean-4.8

Median-5

Mode-5

Appendix L

"I try to achieve perfection to avoid chances of failing or disapproval."

	A-ADHD	B-Control
Respondent 1	7	7
Respondent 2	7	7
Respondent 3	7	6
Respondent 4	5	6
Respondent 5	4	6
Respondent 6	6	7
Respondent 7	6	7
Respondent 8	5	6
Respondent 9	3	6
Respondent 10	4	2
Respondent 11	6	7
Respondent 12	6	6
Respondent 13	7	6
Respondent 14	7	7
Respondent 15	6	3
Respondent 16	4	5
Respondent 17	6	6
Respondent 18	7	7
Respondent 19	6	7
Respondent 20	6	7

$F(1, 38) = 0.55, p = .465, \eta^2 = 0.01.$

A. Mean-5.75

Median-6

Mode-6

B. Mean-6.05

Median-6

Mode-7

Appendix M

"I perceive people's neutral reactions in tone or body language as rejection."

	A-ADHD	B-Control
Respondent 1	4	6
Respondent 2	7	6
Respondent 3	5	5
Respondent 4	6	3
Respondent 5	3	2
Respondent 6	6	4
Respondent 7	5	6
Respondent 8	6	5
Respondent 9	4	3
Respondent 10	6	4
Respondent 11	5	6
Respondent 12	5	5
Respondent 13	5	5
Respondent 14	7	5
Respondent 15	5	2
Respondent 16	4	7
Respondent 17	6	5
Respondent 18	6	6
Respondent 19	7	7
Respondent 20	6	6

$F(1, 38) = 1.47, p = .233, \eta^2 = 0.04.$

A. Mean-5.4

Median-5.5

Mode-6

B. Mean-4.9

Median-5

Mode-6,5

Appendix N

"My parents/guardians spoke or acted negatively in regard to my ADHD symptoms."

	A-ADHD
Respondent 1	2
Respondent 2	2
Respondent 3	3
Respondent 4	5
Respondent 5	1
Respondent 6	3
Respondent 7	6
Respondent 8	7
Respondent 9	2
Respondent 10	6
Respondent 11	6
Respondent 12	5
Respondent 13	6
Respondent 14	7
Respondent 15	5
Respondent 16	1
Respondent 17	7
Respondent 18	5
Respondent 19	7
Respondent 20	4

A. Mean-4.5

Median-5

Mode-5,6,7

Appendix O

"My parents/guardians provided me with the ability to receive medication in my early childhood."

	A-ADHD
Respondent 1	4
Respondent 2	1
Respondent 3	4
Respondent 4	2
Respondent 5	5
Respondent 6	4
Respondent 7	5
Respondent 8	6
Respondent 9	6
Respondent 10	2
Respondent 11	2
Respondent 12	2
Respondent 13	4
Respondent 14	7
Respondent 15	6
Respondent 16	6
Respondent 17	5
Respondent 18	5
Respondent 19	4
Respondent 20	4

A. Mean-4.2

Median-4

Mode-4

Appendix P

"My parents/guardians provided me with the ability to receive counseling in early childhood."

	A-ADHD
Respondent 1	4
Respondent 2	3
Respondent 3	5
Respondent 4	2
Respondent 5	7
Respondent 6	4
Respondent 7	2
Respondent 8	5
Respondent 9	2
Respondent 10	2
Respondent 11	2
Respondent 12	2
Respondent 13	4
Respondent 14	7
Respondent 15	5
Respondent 16	4
Respondent 17	5
Respondent 18	7
Respondent 19	4
Respondent 20	4

A. Mean-4
Median-4
Mode-4,2

Appendix Q

"In elementary school I was constantly told to try harder."

	A-ADHD	B-Control
Respondent 1	2	7
Respondent 2	6	2
Respondent 3	3	3
Respondent 4	6	2
Respondent 5	7	5
Respondent 6	7	4
Respondent 7	7	6
Respondent 8	5	4
Respondent 9	6	2
Respondent 10	6	1
Respondent 11	2	3
Respondent 12	4	2
Respondent 13	5	2
Respondent 14	7	5
Respondent 15	7	2
Respondent 16	4	4
Respondent 17	1	4
Respondent 18	2	4
Respondent 19	6	7
Respondent 20	4	4

$F(1, 38) = 4.17, p = .048, \eta^2 = 0.10.$

A. Mean-4.85

Median-5.5

Mode-6,7

B. Mean-3.65

Median-4

Mode-2,4

Appendix R

"In elementary school I was constantly told to just pay attention."

	A-ADHD	B-Control
Respondent 1	2	6
Respondent 2	7	4
Respondent 3	6	1
Respondent 4	7	2
Respondent 5	7	2
Respondent 6	7	2
Respondent 7	7	6
Respondent 8	7	5
Respondent 9	7	2
Respondent 10	7	1
Respondent 11	2	3
Respondent 12	5	3
Respondent 13	6	3
Respondent 14	7	7
Respondent 15	7	2
Respondent 16	5	3
Respondent 17	1	3
Respondent 18	2	2
Respondent 19	6	6
Respondent 20	5	5

$F(1, 38) = 11.65, p = .002, \eta^2 = 0.23.$

A. Mean-5.5

Median-6.5

Mode-7

B. Mean-3.4

Median-3

Mode-2

Appendix S

"In school I was constantly told to sit still."

	A-ADHD	B-Control
Respondent 1	5	5
Respondent 2	7	2
Respondent 3	6	2
Respondent 4	7	2
Respondent 5	7	2
Respondent 6	7	2
Respondent 7	5	5
Respondent 8	6	4
Respondent 9	7	2
Respondent 10	6	1
Respondent 11	2	7
Respondent 12	6	2
Respondent 13	6	2
Respondent 14	7	6
Respondent 15	7	2
Respondent 16	4	2
Respondent 17	4	2
Respondent 18	2	2
Respondent 19	6	5
Respondent 20	5	7

$F(1, 38) = 18.87, p < .001, \eta^2 = 0.33.$

A. Mean-5.6

Median-6

Mode-7

B. Mean-3.2

Median-2

Mode-2

Appendix T

"On school report cards I was labeled as inconsistent in work."

	A-ADHD	B-Control
Respondent 1	2	4
Respondent 2	6	2
Respondent 3	6	2
Respondent 4	6	1
Respondent 5	5	2
Respondent 6	7	1
Respondent 7	7	2
Respondent 8	2	2
Respondent 9	4	1
Respondent 10	5	1
Respondent 11	3	5
Respondent 12	4	3
Respondent 13	4	3
Respondent 14	1	6
Respondent 15	7	2
Respondent 16	4	1
Respondent 17	1	2
Respondent 18	2	2
Respondent 19	4	2
Respondent 20	2	6

$F(1, 38) = 7.92, p = .008, \eta^2 = 0.17.$

A. Mean-41

Median-4

Mode-4

B. Mean-2.5

Median-2

Mode-2

Appendix U

"On school report cards I was said to struggle staying on task."

	A-ADHD	B-Control
Respondent 1	6	5
Respondent 2	7	2
Respondent 3	6	2
Respondent 4	7	1
Respondent 5	7	2
Respondent 6	7	1
Respondent 7	7	4
Respondent 8	5	2
Respondent 9	6	1
Respondent 10	6	1
Respondent 11	2	7
Respondent 12	4	1
Respondent 13	6	1
Respondent 14	7	7
Respondent 15	7	2
Respondent 16	4	1
Respondent 17	4	5
Respondent 18	2	3
Respondent 19	7	2
Respondent 20	6	6

$F(1, 38) = 23.08, p < .001, \eta^2 = 0.38.$

A. Mean-5.65

Median-6

Mode-7

B. Mean-2.8

Median-2

Mode-1

Appendix V

"On school report cards I was said to be disruptive in class."

	A-ADHD	B-Control
Respondent 1	5	2
Respondent 2	7	3
Respondent 3	5	3
Respondent 4	5	1
Respondent 5	2	2
Respondent 6	7	1
Respondent 7	6	1
Respondent 8	2	2
Respondent 9	7	1
Respondent 10	6	3
Respondent 11	2	5
Respondent 12	5	1
Respondent 13	5	1
Respondent 14	7	7
Respondent 15	1	2
Respondent 16	1	1
Respondent 17	3	1
Respondent 18	1	2
Respondent 19	2	2
Respondent 20	4	1

$F(1, 38) = 11.54, p = .002, \eta^2 = 0.23.$

A. Mean-4.15

Median-5

Mode-5

B. Mean-2.1

Median-2

Mode-1

Appendix W

"On school report cards I was told I don't engage in class discussions enough."

	A-ADHD	B-Control
Respondent 1	2	5
Respondent 2	3	3
Respondent 3	3	1
Respondent 4	3	7
Respondent 5	7	5
Respondent 6	7	7
Respondent 7	7	7
Respondent 8	3	3
Respondent 9	2	1
Respondent 10	5	5
Respondent 11	7	4
Respondent 12	4	1
Respondent 13	3	1
Respondent 14	1	1
Respondent 15	6	2
Respondent 16	4	3
Respondent 17	1	1
Respondent 18	6	2
Respondent 19	7	5
Respondent 20	4	1

$F(1, 38) = 2.14, p = .152, \eta^2 = 0.05.$

A. Mean-4.25

Median-4

Mode-3,7

B. Mean-3.25

Median-3

Mode-1

Appendix X

"I have been told "everyone has a little bit of ADHD.""

	A-ADHD
Respondent 1	2
Respondent 2	7
Respondent 3	7
Respondent 4	5
Respondent 5	4
Respondent 6	7
Respondent 7	6
Respondent 8	2
Respondent 9	2
Respondent 10	6
Respondent 11	5
Respondent 12	7
Respondent 13	7
Respondent 14	6
Respondent 15	6
Respondent 16	4
Respondent 17	6
Respondent 18	4
Respondent 19	7
Respondent 20	5

A. Mean-5.25

Median-6

Mode-7

Appendix Y

"I felt misunderstood as a child."

	A-ADHD	B-Control
Respondent 1	2	6
Respondent 2	7	5
Respondent 3	6	4
Respondent 4	5	6
Respondent 5	6	2
Respondent 6	7	4
Respondent 7	7	5
Respondent 8	6	6
Respondent 9	2	2
Respondent 10	6	3
Respondent 11	7	6
Respondent 12	7	2
Respondent 13	7	2
Respondent 14	7	6
Respondent 15	7	5
Respondent 16	3	7
Respondent 17	7	7
Respondent 18	5	7
Respondent 19	7	4
Respondent 20	5	7

$F(1, 38) = 3.26, p = .079, \eta^2 = 0.08$

A. Mean-5.8

Median-6.5

Mode-7

B. Mean-4.8

Median-5

Mode-6

Appendix Z

"In my childhood I was constantly told I was weird."

	A-ADHD	B-Control
Respondent 1	2	3
Respondent 2	7	4
Respondent 3	5	4
Respondent 4	7	5
Respondent 5	5	2
Respondent 6	6	4
Respondent 7	7	2
Respondent 8	7	4
Respondent 9	5	3
Respondent 10	7	1
Respondent 11	7	6
Respondent 12	6	2
Respondent 13	5	2
Respondent 14	7	5
Respondent 15	7	2
Respondent 16	5	6
Respondent 17	7	4
Respondent 18	6	5
Respondent 19	7	2
Respondent 20	7	5

$F(1, 38) = 33.06, p < .001, \eta^2 = 0.47.$

A. Mean-6.1

Median-7

Mode-7

B. Mean-3.55

Median-4

Mode-2

Appendix AA

"In my childhood I did not have many close friends."

	A-ADHD	B-Control
Respondent 1	2	1
Respondent 2	7	3
Respondent 3	4	6
Respondent 4	4	3
Respondent 5	6	4
Respondent 6	7	4
Respondent 7	7	2
Respondent 8	7	4
Respondent 9	5	1
Respondent 10	4	4
Respondent 11	7	7
Respondent 12	1	1
Respondent 13	6	1
Respondent 14	1	3
Respondent 15	5	2
Respondent 16	5	5
Respondent 17	7	2
Respondent 18	4	7
Respondent 19	7	4
Respondent 20	7	2

$F(1, 38) = 8.86, p = .005, \eta^2 = 0.19.$

A. Mean-5.15

Median-5.5

Mode-7

B. Mean-3.3

Median-3

Mode-4

Appendix AB

"In my childhood I did not receive enough support for my ADHD."

	A-ADHD
Respondent 1	6
Respondent 2	7
Respondent 3	6
Respondent 4	5
Respondent 5	4
Respondent 6	6
Respondent 7	6
Respondent 8	5
Respondent 9	2
Respondent 10	6
Respondent 11	7
Respondent 12	7
Respondent 13	7
Respondent 14	5
Respondent 15	6
Respondent 16	2
Respondent 17	7
Respondent 18	5
Respondent 19	7
Respondent 20	4

A. Mean-5.5

Median-6

Mode-6,7

Appendix AC

"I was yelled at by my parents/guardians in childhood."

	A-ADHD	B-Control
Respondent 1	6	6
Respondent 2	7	6
Respondent 3	5	6
Respondent 4	4	4
Respondent 5	5	5
Respondent 6	6	1
Respondent 7	7	5
Respondent 8	7	5
Respondent 9	2	2
Respondent 10	7	6
Respondent 11	7	7
Respondent 12	7	2
Respondent 13	7	2
Respondent 14	7	7
Respondent 15	7	5
Respondent 16	5	7
Respondent 17	7	7
Respondent 18	2	6
Respondent 19	7	7
Respondent 20	2	6

$F(1, 38) = 1.02, p = .319, \eta^2 = 0.03.$

A. Mean-5.7

Median-7

Mode-7

B. Mean-5.1

Median-6

Mode-6